

Thiodiazines. Part VIII. Action of Ethyl α -Chloroacetoacetate upon Thiosemicarbazides.

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The interaction of 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides and ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate leads to the formation of well defined crystalline products, having the general formula, $R \cdot C_5H_6O_2N_3S$ showing that the ester grouping takes part in the condensation. This is rather remarkable in view of the fact that the keto-group of the ester takes part in ring formation when thiocarbamide is employed (Zürcher, *Annalen*, 1889, 250, 281). The products were found to be insoluble in sodium carbonate but soluble in alkali. They yielded well defined hydrochlorides and acetyl derivatives; the latter were insoluble in alkali and could be easily de-acetylated to the original substances by the action of aqueous-alcoholic hydrochloric acid. They failed to condense with phenylhydrazine or semicarbazide under the usual conditions. Moreover, they could not be made to condense with aldehydes or ketones. They did not impart any characteristic coloration to ferric chloride. These facts suggest the following formula as a possible structure for these condensation products.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Methylthiosemicarbazide and Ethyl α -Chloroacetoacetate.—4-Methylthiosemicarbazide (3 g.) was dissolved in 50 c.c. of dry absolute alcohol and ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate (4.7 g.) was added and the mixture shaken for half an hour. Reaction took place with evolution of heat. The whole was then refluxed for about

20 minutes on the water-bath to complete the reaction. On evaporation of the solvent at the ordinary temperature, yellowish crystals separated out. These were collected and dried over porous plate (2.6 g.). The free base was then isolated by extracting the product with hot 5—7% hydrochloric acid and then treating the extract with a very dilute solution of sodium carbonate. The colourless crystals (1.8 g.) thus obtained were recrystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 156°. The base dissolved in hot aqueous alkali. (Found: C, 38.68; H, 4.99; N, 22.27. $C_6H_9O_2N_3S$ requires C, 38.50; H, 4.81; N, 22.44 per cent.). It is soluble in acetic acid, and acetone, sparingly in benzene and insoluble in chloroform and ether.

The *acetyl* derivative, crystallised in long colourless needles melting at 65°. It is insoluble in aqueous alkali. (Found: N, 18.51. $C_8H_{11}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 18.34 per cent.). The *hydrochloride* separated from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 197°. (Found: Cl, 15.6. $C_6H_{10}O_2N_3S\text{Cl}$ requires Cl, 15.88 per cent.).

4-isoButylthiosemicarbazide and Ethyl α -Chloroacetoacetate.—The procedure was identical. The base crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles melting at 145°. (Found: C, 47.26; H, 6.39; N, 18.18. $C_9H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires C, 47.11; H, 6.55; N, 18.34 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* melted at 158°. The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from methyl alcohol (needles), m. p. 240°. (Found: C, 48.51; H, 6.39; N, 15.61. $C_{11}H_{17}O_3N_3S$ requires C, 48.70; H, 6.27; N, 15.49 per cent.).

4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide and Ethyl α -Chloroacetoacetate.—Prepared in the usual manner it crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles melting at 166°. It is also soluble in chloroform and ether. (Found: C, 53.5; H, 4.7; N, 16.89. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_3S$ requires C, 52.9; H, 4.4; N, 16.86 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 149°. (Found: N, 14.9. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_3S\text{Cl}$ requires N, 14.71 per cent.). The *acetyl* derivative formed almost colourless needles, m. p. 118°. (Found: C, 53.88; H, 4.67; N, 14.70. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_3S$ requires C, 53.60; H, 4.47; N, 14.4 per cent.).

Hydrolysis.—One g. of the *acetyl* derivative was dissolved in aqueous alcohol and refluxed on the water-bath after the addition of an excess of hydrochloric acid. On cooling the solution was diluted and made alkaline with sodium carbonate. The free base

was collected and on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 166° alone or when mixed with the above phenyl compound.

4-o-Tolylthiosemicarbazide and Ethyl α -Chloroacetoacetate.—The condensation product was obtained as usual. It was finally crystallised from alcohol in beautiful, long needles, m. p. 165°. (Found: N, 15·87. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 15·97 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative formed colourless plates from alcohol, m. p. 175°. (Found: N, 13·58. $C_{14}H_{15}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 13·77 per cent.). The *hydrochloride* crystallised from alcohol in silky needles melting at 147°.

4-p-Tolylthiosemicarbazide and Ethyl α -Chloroacetoacetate.—The product formed slender needles from alcohol, m. p. 181°. (Found: N, 16·07. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 15·97 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from absolute alcohol in colourless needles melting at 124°. (Found: C, 55·18; H, 5·20; N, 13·49. $C_{14}H_{15}O_3N_3S$ requires C, 55·08; H, 4·91; N, 13·77 per cent.).

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